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Research Article

**HOW TO GENERATE LOYALTY THROUGH SERVICE
QUALITY IN PHARMACIES? MEDIATING ROLE OF TRUST**¹Ahsan Zubair, ²Faiqa Kiran, ³Irum Shahzadi, ⁴Muhammad A. Hussain Mahmood¹Government College University Faisalabad, ahsanzubair4002@gmail.com²Government College University Faisalabad³Government College University Faisalabad⁴Graduate, School of Business, Universiti Kebangsaan, Malaysia**Abstract:**

Present study was conducted to analyze the influence of service quality on loyalty in pharmacies along with the mediating role of trust. Customers are more conscious about quality of services especially in case of purchasing medicines. Trust is also an important part to enhance the loyalty of customers in pharmacies. For the purpose of data collection non-probability convenient sampling was used. After analysis of data it was found that there was positive and significant impact of service quality on trust as well as loyalty of customers. Furthermore it also found that trust also has a positive relationship with customer loyalty. Further analysis shows that trust plays a role as mediator between the relationship of service quality and loyalty of the customers. Findings of this study will help to policy makers or marketing managers of pharmaceutical chains to understand the importance of service quality which leads to loyalty of customers.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Loyalty, Trust, Pharmaceutical chains***Corresponding author:****Ahsan Zubair,**

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INTRODUCTION:

In the present era where marketing conditions are changing constantly, organizations must realize that the growing economic system. In such condition every customer gained a new value. So the customer satisfaction is an element that encourage the use of services again and again but there is no guaranty that a satisfied customer make a purchase (1). Marketers just focus on customer satisfaction not on increased customer satisfaction during 1980s and 1990s, but marketers realize with the passage of time that many customers who satisfy with the services not repurchase or reuse the products. When customer make repurchases with the same brands profitability raises so to maintain the position of the organizations loyalty of the customers is very important. In today's modern market brand loyalty is very much important to enhance the profitability of the firm as well as to stay competitive in the existence market (2). During the last three decades marketers have recognized the importance of brand loyalty through the available marketing literature (3). In this connection, (4) has expressed that impact of loyalty on the process of brand equity has been observed that brand loyalty creates a lot of advantages for the marketers such as attract new customers, to reduce marketing cost and increase the market share. Mostly organizations hold their customer as a competitive asset suggested by many investigations. Increasing competition among the pharmaceutical chains has realized the importance of service quality by the marketers. Customer loyalty determined as the important part in financial growth of pharmaceutical chains and competing the other organization and they keep their place in the market, (5) study show the strong relation within customer and desertion to increasing the growth of the organization. Many researchers concluded that they keep their loyal customer as an aggressive asset. In reality the customer have many choices in the current competitive environment. This is the reason that customer chose their favorite options from available alternatives. The loyalty is assumed as a valuable component for the success of any pharmaceutical chain in the present competitive environment. Another way we say that as the loyal customer increases the profitability also increases. Emerging a new chain of pharmacies including life Pharmacy, Asif Pharma, Noor Pharmaceuticals etc. and their dedications to opening new branches in different cities is an indication of the problem. With increasing number of customer in the competitive environment there is no guarantee of profit rather than retaining the existing customers is most important than creating new ones. The aim of this study is to find the factors that contribute in the customer loyalty in the pharmaceutical industry and provide guidelines to

increase the loyalty build relationships with customers and enhance customer commitment.

Medical science has been advancing rapidly and making its best effort to remedy the new disease by developing new products or adding various ingredients. As a result the similar disease with few new indications is needed to be cured with an advanced combination of ingredients which ultimately result in the increase of similar products mitigating the shares of previous products. For instance, Panadol and Panadol Extra, there isn't any specific difference in the ingredients but the difference lies in the strength. Therefore, to safeguarding as well as sustaining the image of an organization, marketers are severely engaged in maintaining their product portfolios. Nonetheless, another major reason in to be actively engaged in maintaining an efficient portfolio is because of the industrial competition. As discussed above the acute intensity of competition in this industry; for a company to have multiple brands, it becomes a challenging task for marketers to uphold their brand portfolio efficient. Whenever a medical representative calls the physicians/doctors, it becomes very difficult to instill all the brands in his/her mind for increased prescriptions, which may result in the acknowledgement of few brands of one company, while appreciation of some brands of another company. Yet the highly challenging and chaotic situations led marketers to ponder on their brand portfolio strategy for enhanced organizational performance.

Pharmaceutical sector in Pakistan has been considered one of the fundamental economic drivers that contributes a lot in Pakistan's overall economic growth, yet to some extent brand portfolio strategy is not being efficiently executed in this industry. The researcher has visited a number of pharmaceutical companies in order to conduct preliminary investigation about this predicament. Various managers at senior and/or operational levels and analysts have been consulted for this purpose and based on their views it is revealed that brand portfolio strategy and brand management is an eminent factor for enhanced organizational performance as well as it results in increased organizational sustainability in the long run. Similarly, product cannibalism as an important component of brand portfolio strategy and brand positioning are considered the most challenging as well as valuable strategies if executed efficiently to enhance organizational performance.

Problem Identification

As discussed above the importance of pharmaceutical industry in Pakistan's economic growth and the

strength and diversity of challenges it's been facing, the research on brand portfolio management is an area of concern for both researchers and practitioners which invites a lot more to ponder and frowningly investigate the impacts of brand portfolio strategy in firm performance. Based on pharmaceuticals' surveys and numerous brain storming sessions the researcher found that brand portfolio strategy has counted a paramount importance in the success and growth of pharmaceutical sector to outperform such a sundry competition. Various brand managers have been consulted and their reviews have been taken which enlighten and focus on the extreme significance of brand portfolio strategy in firm performance. Further, the reasoning behind the remarkable importance of brand management has come into notice due to an increased competition as there are around 700 pharmaceutical companies operating in Pakistan. This enormous figure signals a huge competition amongst each other.

There is a greater extent of challenge prevailing in pharmaceutical industry to get the marketing rights and the overwhelming scenario is this challenge is growing rapidly. Pharmaceutical companies are probed to do more with less every day. Due to shortening period of exclusivity, in less time a higher sale is asked. Brand managers are questioned to get higher margins despite of lesser price flexibility and proliferation of products and stakeholders. There exist a less clinical differentiation amongst the products and higher market equity is demanded. Totaling to these complications are the managerial concerns that encumber pharmaceutical companies. Therefore, taken into account all the challenges faced every day by brand managers and marketing personnel; the dilemma gives notion and meaning to reason the connotation of brand portfolio strategy in order to harvest exceptional results.

Significance of the study

For the economic stability and development and growth of a country or nation loyalty is the important part this research study describe the importance of the loyalty and help the people to know the importance of the loyalty in different articles the loyalty is an important factor for developing, economic stability of a country or nation we analyze different sources and conclude these research describe the factor effecting on the loyalty and this research describe the importance of the loyalty and benefit of the build long term relationship with the customer and this research helps the marketer to develop and attract the loyal consumer and how they marketer develop the habit of loyalty in consumer.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

(6) defined product cannibalism as a process the sales of an existing product is shared by a new product by deviating the existing products. In addition, (7) provided the following definition: repositioning strategies or product line extension cause no or minimal failure risk for the new product which is being introduced; however it poses detrimental effects to the existing products sales and market share and this should be considered in product extension strategic outlook.

Studies also suggest that the overlap/intra-portfolio competition may be within products and across the products tiers. Usually, the product line of organizations is not very large and the profits can be increased by the addition of new products in the product line. On the contrary product line can be very large and the profits can be increased by pruning the product line. (6) suggested that the product line therefore should be large or small depend on the identification of the additional benefits providing to the firm in either situation.

The literature reveals that there are various benefits in intra-portfolio competition. Firstly, intra-portfolio competition allows an organization to meet the target market's requirement by offering a variety of alternatives with minimum differentiations hence resulting in increased market share (8). Especially in pharmaceutical industry, each disease with demanding a slightly advanced remedies for its cure e.g. an extension in the one or two ingredients or doubling the strength of the medicine. Hence, by doing so the product line can be enhanced which will allow a deeper market share if the alternative product has already achieved a worthy market share. Secondly, the intra-portfolio competition results in deterring new rivals to enter the market as there already prevail abundant of alternatives intra-organizationally and intra-industrially. Thirdly, the most important benefit associated with intra-portfolio competition is lowering the risk of customer switching behavior of one companies' products (9). (10) pointed out that positive quality affiliations with the brands and the perceived quality are interlinked and strengthen organizational portfolio in the minds of customers. Customers are usually more conscious to the risk factor and those which provide high risk reduction value due to the higher brand quality enjoy superior customers' appreciation and results in increased market share (11). Though high quality brands may have higher prices yet they may enjoy greater price premiums (4). In particular, those brands which possess high quality enjoy high acknowledgement and results in increased profit for companies as a result of certain marketing actions such as price promotions (12).

Loyalty: In today's modern market brand loyalty is very much important to enhance the profitability of the firm as well as to stay competitive in the existence market (2). Every organization desires to have its brands with high customer loyalty. It is a sad fact that all the brands cannot be able to attain the highest level of loyalty. To develop and maintain the brand loyalty is the main focused and center point of the planning of every organization. (13). During the last three decades marketers has recognized the importance of brand loyalty through the available marketing literature (3). In this connection, (4) has expressed that impact of loyalty on the process of brand equity has been observed that brand loyalty creates a lot of advantages for the marketers such as attract new customers, to reduce marketing cost and increase the market share. (14) discussed that marketing advantages based on loyalty, positive word of mouth and a large resistance among the loyal consumers to develop competitive policies. Although there are significant managerial implications of brand loyalty yet a huge gap of conceptual and empirical findings. Specifically, with some exceptions (15) our concepts related to brand loyalty are limited only behaviors of the customers there is lack of behavioral dimensions and its association with other factors at the level of consumer and market. Brand loyalty refers to the priorities of consumers while they intend to buy only a specific brand or a product, this loyalty is the result of quality provided by the brand and very less role of the price of product or brand (16) . Loyalty to brand can be effected by the attitude and habit of the brand (17) it is also differentiate from either attitudes. Brand loyalty can also be determined through customer satisfaction along with the performance of brand.

Service quality: The service quality main purpose examines carefully that perception of consumer about the service elements like physical environment, interaction quality and the quality of outcome. Service quality dimensions (reliability, assurance, responsiveness, empathy) are bases to evaluate the service elements and tangibles. (18) depicted service quality *as worldwide phenomena or behavior which relates to the superior quality services provided* ' another definition of service quality is" *the level of degree of difference between customers' actual expectations related to the service and their expectations about the performance of service*". (19) perceived judgment of service quality of any organization and resulting evaluation process is start where customer compares *the expectations of customers related to the services they received according to their perception*. (20) suggested that the implication and conceptualization of service quality was not sufficient and cited adequate marketing

literature (21) supporting performance-based simple measures of service quality. (15) the customers behavioral intention in service develop the comprehensive, and multi-dimensional framework. Initially this framework adjusting four main types like purchase intention, price sensitivity word of mouth and complaining behavior.

Trust: (22) contend that *"the variable most universally accepted trust as a basis of any human interaction"*. (23) give a Definition of trust that *the degree of willingness that the consumer trust on the ability of brand that it perform its stated function* "This definition has two general approaches to trust in the literature (24). First, dimension as the trust viewed as a belief, sentiment, or expectation relate to the partner's trustworthiness that are concluded from the other partner expertise, reliability, or expectation about an exchange partner's trustworthiness that results from the partner's expertise, reliability, or intentionality. Second aspect of trust Viewed as behavioral dimension indicate that rely on a partner and unreliability on the part of trustee. (25) also focus that the notion of trust is related only in condition of uncertainty when small difference are n brands. Especially in environment of criticism they can rely on trusted brands and reduce uncertainty. (25) argues that the trust construction involve a "calculation process" depend on the brand ability of an object to continue to fulfill its responsibility and the estimate of a reward against the estimated cost stay along in relationship. On the other hand, they argue that the trust influence the firm to act in the best interest of their customers based on share values and goals. Thus, beliefs about important facets of trust like reliability, safety, and honesty that people incorporate in their operationalization of trust, as we discuss latter. So, we consciously consider of any brand trust as it involve process. Customer Trust generally develops through the following five stages: 1. *enlargement*, 2. *Suspension*, 3. *responsiveness*, 4. *commitment*, and 5. *investigation*, (26). Customer trust on a certain brand is the determinant of the future purchase intentions of a customer and it is an important factor to maintain a profitable relationship with customer.

Service quality and trust: According to (26), usually the customer chooses the brand they believe is reliable and trustworthy. Another researcher (27) claims that the consumer is aware of the brand's quality of service when evaluating overall quality of service. He argues that the quality of service differs from consumer expectations between service quality and how the customer discovers the quality of service. Some other researchers such as (28) explain that there are some differences between expected and observed

performance, which is the best indicator of customer satisfaction, leading to the level of customer confidence. He gives an example that when a consumer sometimes buys different brands, they can change these brands because they are not completely satisfied with the brand and that they have more expectations with other brands. (27) suggested that service quality is sufficient when consumer perceptions of brands are equal to or greater than consumer perceptions. Service quality means service superiority at a certain level of service.

Trust and Loyalty: *"It is no longer sufficient to concentrate only on customer satisfaction; the next step is loyalty"* a definition given by (29). It is apparent that the trust has a positive effect on customer orientation, if consumers trust companies' products and services in return, they are more loyal to the organization in question. The survey was conducted in Bangladesh among consumers in the telecommunications sector. They claim that if consumers are sure that they are loyal (30). (31) showed that the results supported the hypothesis and showed that the confidentiality site is the foundation of web site loyalty. But the results also showed that the level of experience of the brand effect of online trust and fidelity in different ways depending on the customer's connection brand. (32) study reveal optometric practice environments; consumer confidence is a significant correlation with consumer loyalty, whose providers offer the greatest efforts and intentions to consumers who are more trusted in the organization's services and more loyal. Another researcher found the trust and loyalty of the positive correlation that they had a positive effect on consumer confidence in organizations where organizations have developed social identity, leading to consumer loyalty organization (33). (34) explain trust as the exchange partner has credibility and the other party trusts the exchange partner.

(35) discussed that a partner's willingness to trust the stock exchange partner is that one party to trust. The trading partner's business benefits one of the partners remembered by (36). (25) said that related parties include customers who use the customer-cost-to-benefit relationship to the customer's responsibility. Attitude and customer behavior affect two aspects of customer loyalty. The offer or the additional services and products to obtain and could buy back the intention of purchasing the same company's products represents this concept of customer attitude, could willingness to recommend other companies that indicate the customer's commitment to the company to show resistance to switching patterns to competitors and accepted to pay higher prices for products (15).

On the one hand, customer loyalty represents the same or different goods and services from the same company, the same company and advised other customers to buy their products if the same company and the likelihood of choosing that brand for a long time (37). (38) conducted empirical research which states that our customers' confidence in improving customer loyalty by testing him that trust customers have a direct impact on loyalty. Customers rely on an organization that leads to loyalty.

(39) define the future fidelity "deeply bound to preserve the desired product or service consistently, where repeat the same product or of the same brand acquisition cause efforts and despite shifting behavior on the market despite the impact. Many studies have described the benefits of good faith. (15) describes the quality of service "increased number of withdrawals, better shopping courses in positive word of mouth and sensitivity once the price has risen." This recognizes the influence of Quality of loyalty service. Some previous studies show that service quality affects consumer loyalty through the company and brand credibility (40). Some other studies show that service quality directly impacts customer loyalty due to customer image or customer safety. Establishing trust is a challenging task for researchers because there is no exact term and there are verifications in the contract. Research suggests that normal use and satisfaction with the product or service in general is related to loyalty. (15) describes the quality of service "Increased withdrawal amount, adding improved purchase rates relative to the positive word of mouth of this restaurant and price sensitivity is higher. Some previous studies have shown that loyalty is based on the quality of service (41). Some other studies show that service quality directly affects customer loyalty because of customer image or customer satisfaction. Determining trust is a challenging task for researchers because the exact term is not available and there is a contract inspection. Research shows that the product and service are often satisfied with the product or service.

Mediating Role of Trust: Having considered the quality of service prior evaluations Credibility and trust can be considered as intermediaries in relation to the quality and reliability of the service that convey trust. They require the role of trust in a broker or interviews if the restaurant held five service qualities. (42) Identified five service qualities (i.e. reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangible new) As a result of the five the quality of these services fidelity social identity loyalty in the central part of the variable trust a mediator. In addition, loyalty is not only a solid if realized, assessment outside the

company could power also affect the organization than on operations without promotional advertising staff to sell publicity because of rationing for the public in the mouth etc. Confidence rate is something broker customer service quality attribution support function and contract consumer decision to buy influence comp on all sides' reliability. Organizations are committed to affecting consumers' purchasing decisions through trust in the reliability of the trust outcome if the customer relies on trust in getting positive words back in the form of purchases. Stakeholder-driven attributes affect customers to buy back and save word of mouth a positive indirect influence on the trust broker of trust has a direct impact on customer engagement and loyalty, after which indirectly effects on price tolerance.

3. MATERIAL & METHODS:

Measures and Sampling Procedure: A self-administered questionnaire was chosen as a research instrument to gather the primary data of service quality, trust, loyalty in Pharmaceutical chains. Constructs in our study developed by using measurement scale adopted from prior studies.

Service quality: In which we use the 22 items of service quality and this items is measure using seven point Likert scale with anchors strongly disagree(=1)strongly agree(=7).

Loyalty: we use the 7 items of loyalty and these items is measure using seven point Likert scale with anchors strongly disagree (=1)strongly agree(=7).

Trust: Trust is used 4 items and this items is measured using five Likert scale with anchors strongly disagree (=1) strongly agree (=5) and this items is used by (34), 'The Commitment-Trust Theory of Relationship Marketing', Journal of Marketing 58, 20–38) from previous studies.

Sample: A total of 150 questionnaires were distributed among Pharmaceutical chains in District Faisalabad. Convenient sampling technique increase the reliability of the data was adopted convenient sampling. In this research study, the questionnaires were distributed directly to the respondents and the research collected completed questionnaires.

Sample Characteristics: Respondents sample selected for this study was individual customers of Pharmaceutical sector in Faisalabad. There are some demographic characteristic of these individual respondents, which included statistical values such as frequency and percentages of different demographic characteristics of respondents. Percentages: 1) Gender, 2) Occupation, 2) Age, 4) income 5) Education, 6) Pharmaceutical chains.

Table 1: Data analysis

Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage %	Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage %
1. Gender			Bachelor	44	29.9
Male	63	42.9	Masters	68	46.3
Female	84	57.1	Other	34	23.1
2.Income			5.Occopation		
Less than 10,000	31	21.1	Student	61	41.5
10,000-30,000	28	19.0	Job holder	85	57.8
31,000-50,000	40	27.2	Other	1	.7
51,000-80,000	29	19.7	6.Brands		
Above 80,000	19	12.9	Care	23	15.6
3.Age			Shiffa	10	6.8
10-20	5	.7	Life	11	7.5
21-25	85	57.8	Pakistan	12	8.2
26-30	40	27.2	Doctor	21	14.3
31-35	16	10.9	Reman	15	10.2
36-40	5	3.4	Noor	18	12.2
Above 40	0	0	English	14	9.5
4.Qualification			UMS	12	8.2
Intermediate	1	.7	Others	11	7.5

According to this statistical value 42.9% male and remaining 57.1% is female in this sample. In occupation 42.5% is student and 57.5% is job holder. As for as age related .7% fall under age 10-20 years and 57.8% fall under age group 21-25 years and 27.2% under age 26-30 years and 10% fall the age 31-35 and 3% in the age of 36-40. Intermediate are .7% in this sample, bachelor degree holder are up to 29.9%, large number of respondent 46.3% holds master degree in this sample and other degree holder are only 23.1%, most of the respondent 27.2% income is 31000-50000 and 40% respondent below the income 31000-50000 and 31% above the income 31000-50000 at the end 15.6% respondent in care pharmacy 6.8% in Shiffa 7.5% Life 8.2% Pakistan and 14.3% Doctor Pharmacy 10.2% in Rehman 12.2% in Noor 9.5% English Pharmacy 8.2% UMS Pharma 7.5% include the other Pharmaceutical chain response.

Table 2: Regression analysis

Service	R square	Loyalty Significance	Beta
quality	.058	.003	.241

Regression results of loyalty as dependent variable and service quality as independent variable shows positive and significant relation between these two variables at ($p < .001$) significance.

A .Predictor: (constant) service quality

B .Dependent Variable: loyalty

C .Significance at < 0.01

D. N=150

Results show that the model significant at ($p < 0.01$). In which the value of R-Square show the positive rate of change by independent variable (0.058) to dependent variable appropriate at (.241, 0.00). R-Square value shows the variation in loyalty (5.8%) due to change in service quality.

Table 3: Summary

Service	R square	Trust Significance	Beta
Quality	.027	.049	.163

A .Predictor: (constant) service quality

B .Dependent Variable: Trust

C .Significance at < 0.01 D. N=150

Table-4 indications model tested significant at ($p < 0.01$). This results show that the value of R-Square show they positive rate of change by independent variable (0.027) to dependent variable at (0.163) in which the R-Square values describe and show the variation in trust (2.7%) due to change in service quality.

Summary

Loyalty	R square	Significance	Beta
Trust	.367	.000	.606

Regression results of brand trust as independent variable and loyalty as dependent variable shows significant relation between these two variables at ($p < .001$) significance.

A. Predictor: (constant) Trust

B. Dependent Variable: Loyalty

C. Significance at < 0.01

D. N=150

Table 5 significant at ($p < 0.01$) tested the show the modal. In which this table the value of R-Square show the positive rate of change in dependent variable appropriate at (0.606) by independent variable (0.367) and the value of R-Square show the variation in loyalty (36.7%) due to change in trust.

Table 4: Regression analysis

Predictors	Trust		Loyalty	
	B	R ²	B	R ²
Service quality	.163*	.027	.241**	.058

Mediation Analysis: This study is a first attempt to examine the mediating effect trust between service quality and loyalty in pharmaceutical chains. Part of this study the four hypothesis show that H4: trust mediates the relationship of service quality and loyalty. Regression technique was used to test this hypothesis which was recommended by (43). According to them, following condition should be fulfilled. 1. The relationship between independent variable and mediating variable should be significant; 2. The relationship between mediating variable and dependent variable should also be significant. 3. The relationship between independent and dependent variables should also be significant. When these three conditions are fulfilled then researcher goes for further analysis. Perfect mediation is when the independent variable have direct effect on dependent variable i.e. ($\Delta R^2 = .00$) and independent variable should also have ($\beta \neq \text{sig}$).

Table 5: Mediation analysis

Predictors	B	Loyalty	ΔR^2
		R ²	
Mediation Analysis			
Step 1			
Trust		.367	
Step 2			
Service quality	.146	.388	.021*

A. Predictor: (Constant), Trust

B. Predictors: (Constant), Trust, service quality

C. Dependent Variable: Loyalty

D. Significance at <0.01

N=150

The table describe the trust as mediates the relationship between service quality and loyalty in which they fulfill the both condition of mediation which ($\beta \neq \text{sig}$) and ($\Delta R^2 = .00$) so trust play the mediate role between service quality and loyalty .in which ($\Delta R^2 = .021$, $p < 0.01$) and ($\beta = .146$, $p < 0.01$). The value of R- Square describe that (14.6%) change in dependent variables due to independent variables. The H4: trust mediates the relationship of service quality and loyalty.

4.CONCLUSION:

This research study examined the impact of service quality on loyalty: the mediating role of trust. This is a study of pharmaceutical chains in Faisalabad. The main objectives of this study are to discover the mediating role of trust between service quality and loyalty. For this study, researcher was considered only about pharmaceutical chains. Following Pharmacies were selected:

1) Care pharmacy, 2) Shiffa Pharmacy, 3) Life Pharmacy, 4) Pakistan Pharma, 5) Doctor Pharmacy, 6) Rehman Pharmacy, 7) Noor Pharma, 8) English Pharmacy, 9) UMS Pharma and others. The pharmaceutical industry in Pakistan is contributing a lot in economy, it is a highly important segment that

plays a pivotal role in financial sector of Pakistan. Due to high level of competition in pharmaceutical sector, pharmaceutical chains have to be more innovative and more aggressive in developing their product in order to meet the demand of target customer, and to develop trust and customer's attachment with restaurants. The primary data collection method was used questionnaire used this is self-administered questionnaire used for collecting data from 150 customers of different pharmacies. Convenient sampling technique used for sample size. Independent variable is service quality, loyalty is a dependent variable, and trust is mediating variable according to theoretical framework of this study. All these variables were measured by using different point Likert scale which was adopted from previous literature. The Statistical techniques descriptive analysis, Cronbach alpha, correlation analysis, and regression analysis had been used to explore the relationship between variables. Significant results show that the positive and linear relationship among all study variables, the significant level of ($p < \text{value}$) for all study variables is significant at ($p=0.01$) ** level 2 tailed. Results explore that service quality have positive and significant impact on trust and customer loyalty. When we provide the good service

quality to customer developed the trust related this product and then loyal to the pharmaceutical chains. When the trust is developed they take advantage over their competitor in which all relation between variables is significant and positive relation with each other.

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